

Supplementary Table 1. Results of the normality test as presented in Figure 1 (performed using the Shapiro–Wilk test).

miRNA	Type of sample	<i>S-W</i>	<i>p</i>
hsa miR 16 5p	1	0.93	0.140
hsa miR 16 5p	2	0.62	<0.001
hsa miR 222 3p	1	0.97	0.770
hsa miR 222 3p	2	0.81	0.001
hsa miR 21 5p	1	0.97	0.800
hsa miR 21 5p	2	0.76	<0.001
hsa miR 30b 5p	1	0.98	0.980
hsa miR 30b 5p	2	0.86	0.009
hsa miR 17 5p	1	0.98	0.980
hsa miR 17 5p	2	0.86	0.009
hsa miR 18a 5p	1	0.63	<0.001
hsa miR 18a 5p	2	0.46	<0.001
hsa miR 326	1	0.90	0.050
hsa miR 326	2	0.93	0.15
hsa miR 20a 5p	1	0.90	0.050
hsa miR 20a 5p	2	0.93	0.150
hsa miR 27a 3p	1	0.82	0.002
hsa miR 27a 3p	2	0.74	<0.001

miR – microRNA; miRNAs with higher expression in archival samples (1) than in freshly collected samples (2); *N*- number of observation (Type of sample 1 – N=19, Type of sample 2 – N=20); ***S-W***– Shapiro–Wilk test value; *N*- number of observation; ***p*** – level of statistical significance